

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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Deliverable name	Platform integrating information on actionable monogenic and polygenic cancers, with clinical utility in childhood cancers and familial cancers
Deliverable Description	<p>Recommendations; Central EU based information point about actionable cancer predisposition.</p> <p>Target stakeholders for this deliverable are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1) recently started and upcoming European projects, namely EUnetCCC, JANE-2, and JA PCM and2) non-geneticist clinicians and health professionals working in cancer
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- Summary

Up to 10% of cancers are estimated to be derived from a cancer predisposition syndrome (CPS) founded upon germline genetic mutations. New treatment and prevention strategies are being continually developed for this at-risk population, with their implementation dependent on a comprehensive understanding of monogenic mutations and polygenic profiles indicating a CPS from both genetics and non-genetics clinicians. A central EU-based information platform promises to provide an efficient means of disseminating up-to-date information to clinicians across Member States regarding monogenic risk genes and polygenic risk profiles, as well as their actionability. This deliverable report presents recommendations for the location and content of such a platform, illustrated through two use cases: monogenic risk genes in paediatric cancer; and polygenic risk scores in adult breast cancer.

- Objective of the deliverable

Provide recommendations for the location and content of a central EU-based information point about actionable cancer predisposition.

- Work performed

Context

Up to 10% of cancers in paediatric and adult populations are estimated to be derived from a cancer predisposition syndrome (CPS) founded upon germline genetic mutations.^{1,2} Targeting individuals with a CPS, new strategies are being continually developed to improve prevention and treatment prospects in this at-risk population. These strategies depend on a comprehensive understanding from genetics, but also non-genetics, clinicians of the latest information regarding genetic mutations indicating a CPS before enacting best-practice strategies. Increasingly, this information includes both monogenic and polygenic indicators of CPS risk.

Complicating the task for clinicians, knowledge regarding predisposing monogenic mutations and polygenic profiles is often developed within expert genetics and onco-genetics research environments with limited cross-disciplinary diffusion.³ Further, knowledge regarding monogenic risk genes and polygenic risk profiles updates rapidly, and workforce constraints limit the capacity of genetics experts to effectively disseminate information to relevant non-genetics health professionals (e.g. oncologists; general practitioners).⁴ A central EU information point containing up-to-date

information regarding risk genes and genetic profiles, as well as their actionability, promises to simultaneously address all three of these barriers: dissemination; updating; and workforce burden.

Below we detail our recommendations regarding the location and content of this central EU information point, envisioned as a widely accessible digital platform.

Recommendation: Platform Location

Initial work informing platform development (i.e. this deliverable) will be initially hosted on Zenodo, a publicly accessible online resource that hosts the outcomes and deliverables of CAN.HEAL and many other EU projects. However, the ultimate objective is to host this information in a sustainable location designed to be easily accessible to our target audience: physicians and allied health professionals working in cancer across the EU. Recently started and upcoming Joint Actions present two possible final locations for the hosting of this information, with the best fit to be determined over the coming months as more specific details of each project become clear.

The development of a central information platform is a core objective of the recently started Joint Action EUnetCCC (in WP8). KU Leuven, one of two responsible parties for this deliverable, is a part of this Joint Action and can facilitate the prospective integration of monogenic/polygenic risk information into this new portal. Additionally, the team from Hannover Medical School, the other responsible party for this deliverable, is a high contribution partner in the ‘Omics’ Network of Expertise in the JANE-2 project (WP9) which is complementary to EUnetCCC; this team could thus contribute to developing the necessary expert structures required to facilitate the updating of information provided in this portal. NB: Prof. Anke Bergmann and her team from Hannover Medical School are currently in the process of moving to University Clinic Würzburg; this team will participate in JANE-2 as ‘University Clinic Würzburg’ as an affiliated entity of the German Health Ministry.

The upcoming Joint Action on Personalized Cancer Medicine presents another possibility – both KU Leuven and University Clinic Würzburg are included in the preliminary list of participants. Creation of a sustainable, widely accessible information portal would also fit within the context of the activities in WP6 related to enhancing pan-cancer screening and early detection practices across the EU.

Recommendation: Platform Content

The end goal for this platform is to contain the latest information regarding monogenic risk genes and polygenic risk profiles which predispose to a range of cancer types, and applicable to all ages. Further, this platform should integrate insights into specific actions that can be taken when risk genes/profiles are identified. The structure and content of the final platform will be ultimately determined by the needs and construction of the broader EUnetCCC and/or Joint Action Personalized Cancer Medicine platform(s). Accordingly, we have focused on developing a framework for the platform content within the context of two use cases which expand upon insights gained from two CAN.HEAL tasks: monogenic risk genes in paediatric cancers; and polygenic risk scores in breast cancer.

The final platform will expand upon the frameworks described in the two use cases below to encompass monogenic and polygenic risk genes/profiles across all cancer types. In all cases, the information provided in the platform is intended to support a generalized approach to CPS screening which also includes consideration of phenotypic evidence and family history data (e.g. ⁵).

Use case: Monogenic risk genes in paediatric cancers

Risk genes

Risk genes for paediatric cancers to be included in the platform have been identified based on established criteria for assembling a gene panel to evaluate paediatric CPS.⁶ Briefly (for full details see ⁶), these criteria are: 1) a pathogenic variant in a specific gene linked to childhood cancers in a minimum of 5 different children (<18 years old) from at least 2 different families, as well as support for the causal relationship between the gene and cancer development in a minimum of 1 published study; 2) syndromes associated with pathogenic variants in 2 or more different genes, in which at least two of the genes fulfill criteria #1 or >20 cases of childhood cancer with this syndrome have been described and at least 1 study supports a causal relationship between the gene(s) and cancer development.

Genes fulfilling these criteria and to be included in the platform are listed in Table 1 below:

Gene	Syndrome associated with variant (in ≥2 genes)
ABCB11	
A2ML1	Noonan (like) syndrome
ACD	Dyskeratosis congenita
AIP	
ALK	
AMER1	
APC	
ATM	

BAP1	
BLM	
BRAF	Noonan (like) syndrome
BRCA2	Fanconi anemia
BRIP1	Fanconi anemia
BUB1B	Mosaic variegated aneuploidy syndrome
CBL	Noonan (like) syndrome
CD27	
CD70	
CDC73	
CDH1	
CDKN1C	
CDKN2A	
CEBPA	
CEP57	Mosaic variegated aneuploidy syndrome
CREBBP	
CTC1	Dyskeratosis congenita
CTLA4	
CTR9	
DDB2	Xeroderma pigmentosum
DICER1	
DIS3L2	
DKC1	Dyskeratosis congenita
EGLN1 (PHD2)	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
ELGN2 (PHD1)	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
ELP1	
EPAS1 (HIF2A)	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
ERCC2	Xeroderma pigmentosum
ERCC3	Xeroderma pigmentosum
ERCC4	Fanconi anemia
ERCC4	Xeroderma pigmentosum
ERCC5	Xeroderma pigmentosum
ETV6	
EZG2	
FANCA	Fanconi anemia
FANCB	Fanconi anemia
FANCC	Fanconi anemia
FANCD2	Fanconi anemia
FANCE	Fanconi anemia
FANCF	Fanconi anemia
FANCG	Fanconi anemia
FANCI	Fanconi anemia
FANCL	Fanconi anemia
FAS	
FBXW7	
FH	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
GATA2	
GPC3	
GPR161	
HAVCR2	
HRAS	

IKZF1	
ITK	
KRAS	Noonan (like) syndrome
LIG4	
LZTR1	Noonan (like) syndrome
MAP2K1	Noonan (like) syndrome
MAP2K2	Noonan (like) syndrome
MDH2	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
MEN1	
MLH1	Constitutional mismatch repair deficiency (CMMRD) / Lynch syndrome
MSH2	Constitutional mismatch repair deficiency (CMMRD) / Lynch syndrome
MSH6	Constitutional mismatch repair deficiency (CMMRD) / Lynch syndrome
NBN	
NF1	
NF2	
NHP2	Dyskeratosis congenita
NOP10	Dyskeratosis congenita
NRAS	Noonan (like) syndrome
NSD1	
PALB2	Fanconi anemia
PARN	Dyskeratosis congenita
PAX5	
PHOX2B	
PIK3CA	
PMS2	Constitutional mismatch repair deficiency (CMMRD) / Lynch syndrome
POLD1	CMMRD-like phenotype
POLE	
POLH	Xeroderma pigmentosum
PTCH1	Gorlin syndrome
PTEN	
PTPN11	Noonan (like) syndrome
RAF1	Noonan (like) syndrome
RB1	
RECQL4	
REST	
RET	
RIT1	Noonan (like) syndrome
RMRP	
RPL11	Diamond Blackfan anemia
RPL35A	Diamond Blackfan anemia
RPL5	Diamond Blackfan anemia
RPS10	Diamond Blackfan anemia
RPS17	Diamond Blackfan anemia
RPS19	Diamond Blackfan anemia
RPS24	Diamond Blackfan anemia
RPS26	Diamond Blackfan anemia
RPS7	Diamond Blackfan anemia
RRAS	Noonan (like) syndrome
RTKL1	Dyskeratosis congenita
RUNX1	
SAMD9	

SAMD9L	
SBDS	
SDHA	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
SDHAF2	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
SDHB	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
SDHC	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
SDHD	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
SETBP1	
SH2D1A	
SHOC2	Noonan (like) syndrome
SMARCA4	
SMARCB1	
SMARCE1	
SOS1	Noonan (like) syndrome
STK11	
SUFU	Gorlin syndrome
TERC	Dyskeratosis congenita
TERT	Dyskeratosis congenita
TINF2	Dyskeratosis congenita
TP53	
TRIM28	
TRIM37	
TRIP13	Mosaic variegated aneuploidy syndrome
TSC1	
TSC2	
USB1	
VHL	Hereditary paraganglioma-pheochromocytoma
WAS	
WRAP53	Dyskeratosis congenita
WT1	
XPA	Xeroderma pigmentosum
XPC	Xeroderma pigmentosum

Table 1. Monogenic risk genes and associated syndromes for paediatric cancer CPS^{6,7}

Actionability

Upon identification of pathogenic or likely pathogenic variations in one or more of the genes listed above, several actions can be taken depending on the clinical scenario: targeted surveillance/enhanced screening; informing approaches to family planning/reproduction (e.g. in vitro fertilization); management of potential CPS in relatives (e.g. through cascade testing); and targeted therapies.⁸ At present, selection and implementation of appropriate clinical actions is highly context dependent, and no clear single actions can be recommended for specific risk genes across all paediatric cancers. The platform will thus highlight clear actionability for specific risk genes within particular contexts, alongside generalizable recommendations for screening, counselling, and management.

Use case: Polygenic risk scores in breast cancer

Risk Genes

Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS) are emerging as a powerful tool for assessing breast cancer risk. By aggregating the effects of numerous SNPs (single nucleotide polymorphisms), PRS provide a comprehensive risk score that enhances understanding of an individual's genetic predisposition beyond high-risk and moderate-risk susceptibility genes alone.

The platform will feature high and moderate-risk genes for Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer (HBOC), as referenced on the CanRisk website.⁹ Rare pathogenic variants in these genes are risk factors for breast and/or ovarian cancer.

High/moderate risk susceptibility genes (HBOC) featured on the platform	
BRCA1	CHEK2
BRCA2	RAD51D
PALB2	RAD51C
ATM	BARD1
BRIP1	

Moreover, information on the current PRS panel, which includes 313 SNPs, will be integrated into the platform.¹⁰ This SNP panel will be updated regularly following novel discoveries of associated SNPs (e.g. trans-ethnic SNPs, subtype-specific SNPs (e.g. ER-negative versus ER-positive breast cancer), etc.).

Actionability

When pathogenic or likely pathogenic variations are found in any of the listed high and moderate-risk genes, various actions can be taken depending on the clinical context. These actions might include enhanced screening and targeted surveillance, earlier testing of relatives, and applying targeted therapies or even preventive measures (such as mastectomy, etc.). Combining carrier status with PRS refines risk estimates, leading to a more personalized risk stratification and relevant advice. This approach has resulted in notable improvements for women, potentially reducing unnecessary screening, over-treatment, related complications, and anxiety for those with lower-than-expected lifetime risk. Conversely, it identifies higher-risk individuals who benefit from more intensive clinical follow-up to avoid late diagnoses with increased severity and mortality.

There are a few topics that still need to be addressed before PRS can be completely implemented into the clinical setting, and thus PRS information in the platform will be provided with appropriate

caveats. First, the PRS methodology needs further review and optimization to ensure accurate risk calculation. Furthermore, large-scale GWAS (Genome Wide Associations Studies) on diverse populations, especially the African subpopulation, will enhance PRS accuracy and transferability. Importantly, healthcare professionals must be trained to understand and communicate limitations and benefits of PRS for effective clinical integration. Additionally, research on combining PRS with other clinical data (such as mammographic density, history of benign tumor, etc.) and environmental factors is essential for improved risk prediction and personalized medicine. Integrating mixed PRS with electronic health records could facilitate this process. Eventually, building on the foundation established for PRS in breast cancer predisposition this approach can be extended to other cancers (e.g. pancreatic and colon cancer).

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